

Preparation of 7-(α -Aryl- α -4-carbalkoxyanilino) Methyl 8-Quinolinols as Potential Drugs

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Manuscript received 22 September 1975; revised 17 November 1975; accepted 20 November 1975

Some 7-(α -aryl- α -4-carbalkoxy anilino)-methyl-8-quinolinols have been synthesised by a Mannich type of reaction between aldehydes, esters of *p*-amino benzoic acid and 8-quinolinol with a view to study their bactericidal and fungicidal activities as potential drugs.

8-QUINOLINOL and its derivatives are reported as bactericidal¹ and fungicides². Esters of *p*-amino benzoic acid are also known for their antibacterial activity³. Secondary amine, formaldehyde and 8-quinolinol undergo Mannich reaction to yield 7-amino methylloxines. A similar reaction, in which formaldehyde is replaced by aromatic-aldehydes and secondary amines by primary aromatic or heterocyclic amines, has been used to prepare a number of 7-substituted 8-quinolinols. This investigation has been carried out for preparing compounds of the type (A),

where R=phenyl, anisyl, furfuryl, vanillyl, 3-nitrophenyl, 5-bromo vanillyl and R'=ethyl, *n*-propyl and

n-butyl to study their antibacterial and antifungal activities. These title compounds were prepared by carrying out a Mannich type of reaction using an aromatic or heterocyclic aldehyde, an ester of *p*-amino benzoic acid and 8-quinolinol. This reaction fails when R=anisyl and 3-nitrophenyl and R'= *n*-butyl; R=veratryl and R'= ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl.

All the compounds gave characteristic colours with concentrated H₂SO₄, concentrated HNO₃ and 1% FeCl₃.

Experimental

Preparation of 7-(α -aryl- α -4-carbalkoxy anilino) methyl 8-quinolinols⁴ (A): The aldehyde (0.01 M), amine (0.01 M) and 8-quinolinol (0.01 M) were dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) by warming, if necessary, and the mixture stoppered and left for several days at room temperature. The product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol or ethanol-acetone (Table 1).

TABLE 1—7-(α -ARYL- α -4-CARBALKOXY ANILINO)-METHYL-8-QUINOLINOLS (A)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Time of reaction in days	% N Reqd.	Found
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	136	5	7.03	7.40
2.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅	139	14	6.79	7.06
3.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	126	15	6.57	6.41
4.	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	117	20	6.54	6.73
5.	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	113	26	6.33	5.98
6.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅	163	1	9.47	9.72
7.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅	112	1	9.18	8.84
8.	3-CH ₃ O-4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅	158	28	6.30	5.93
9.	3-CH ₃ O-4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	175-7	37	6.11	6.27
10.	3-CH ₃ O-4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅	153	30	5.93	6.28
11.	5-Br-3-CH ₃ O-4-OH.C ₆ H ₂	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ BrN ₂ O ₅	222	21	5.35	5.56
12.	C ₄ H ₉ O	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	146	12	7.21	6.91
13.	C ₄ H ₉ O	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	154	21	6.96	7.32
14.	C ₄ H ₉ O	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	149	32	6.73	7.02

Note: All the compounds give a red colour with conc. H₂SO₄ except 6 which gives a yellow colour, 11 which gives a purple colour and 7, 12, 13, and 14 which give brown colour. With conc. HNO₃, they generally give a yellow colour, but 4 and 5 give red colour while 12, 13 and 14 give blue colour. With FeCl₃, all of them give a green colour.

The time required for the first appearance of a precipitate varied from one day to forty days, usually precipitation continued slowly for many days after this time. All the compounds give characteristic colours with concentrated H_2SO_4 , concentrated HNO_3 and $FeCl_3$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Saurashtra University for providing research facilities and to CSIR, New Delhi for a junior research fellowship to J. N. A.

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